

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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DEVELOPMENT OF GUIDELINES FOR PRESSURE ULCER PREVENTION

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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May 2018

ABSTRACT

Pressure ulcers (PU) cost billions of dollars and tens of thousands of lives each year in the United States (AHRQ, 2014). An acute care, community hospital in Riverside County discovered a number of areas indicating improvement needs following a one-day PU prevalence study in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU), Progressive Care Unit (PCU) and Medical Surgical Unit (MS). These areas included appropriateness of Braden scores to patient condition (presence of PU), frequency and timeliness of skin/risk assessment, number of layers between patient and surface, and appropriate use of support surfaces. The facility did not have formal guidelines, education, or standardized competencies for PU prevention. The purpose of this project was to improve competency in PU risk assessment and prevention by developing local guidelines for PU prevention and providing education based on the guidelines. The Plan Do Study Act (PDSA) model was utilized to carry out this quality improvement project. A convenience sample of registered nurses from the MS, PCU, and ICU units evaluated their own attitudes towards PU prevention in order to allow tailoring of educational offerings. Once guidelines were developed and approved, education was provided to all nurses during annual skills day and new staff orientation. A follow up one-day PU prevalence study was conducted in February 2018.

Results of the project were promising. In 2016, only 55% of patients had a Braden score documented in the previous 12 hours, which is facility policy. For 2018, 90% of patients had Braden scores within the 12-hour window. In 2016, only 29% of HAPU

patients were found to have the recommended two or fewer layers of linen between skin and surface. This jumped to 100% in 2018. The facility now has a formalized plan for preventing PUs as well as improvements in the 2018 one-day prevalence study in the areas of appropriateness of Braden scores to patient condition (presence of pressure ulcer), frequency and timeliness of skin/risk assessment and number of layers between patient and surface. Sustainability is key to any quality improvement project. Education on the PU prevention guidelines will be given to all staff annually. Recommendations have also been made to add the patient's most recent Braden score to the patient report sheet as well as giving nurses the option to identify a patient as high-risk even if the Braden score does not indicate so. These recommendations are being considered on a company-wide level.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to thank everyone who helped me along this journey. Dr. Rachel McClanahan, thank you for the countless hours you spent reading, editing, responding to texts and emails and talking me off the ledge. Dr. Stephanie Vaughn, your support and positive words kept me moving in the right direction.

Dr. Tracy Kasten and Kristina Smith- I will forever be grateful for your guidance and for your time with getting this project going in the facility. You were always there to help me over the next hurdle and I hope you are proud of what we accomplished.

To the friends I still have left after these 100 years of nursing school, I love you and thanks for sticking around!! Maybe we can hang out now...

I want to thank my parents, Steve and Joanne, for always instilling in me a love of learning and an ambitious (if not competitive) nature. Mom, thank you for the babysitting and the moral support. Dad, you encouraged me to apply and I know you are looking down at me, proud as ever. I love you both.

Most importantly I need to thank my husband Tommy and my daughter Yesenia. For all of the times I locked myself away in the office- your love and support are why I am here today. This accomplishment is for all of us! Thank you for always welcoming me home and encouraging me to keep working- even when I didn't always want to. Tom- now it is your turn and Yesenia, soon it will be yours!! I love you guys!!!

BACKGROUND

The development of hospital acquired pressure ulcers (HAPU) has been linked to increased rates of readmission (within 30 days of discharge), increased in-hospital mortality rates, and an increase in mortality rates within 30 days of discharge (Lyder et al., 2012). The average cost to heal a pressure ulcer (PU) can range significantly, depending on severity, from hundreds of dollars to over one hundred thousand dollars (Meddings et al., 2015). According to Meddings et al. (2015), reimbursement for hospitalization was decreased by “an average of \$5,604 per discharge” for Stage III or IV HAPUs (p. 1409).

Preventing PU development and maintaining skin integrity requires staff, patients, and families to be educated and involved in care and prevention strategies. This calls for an interdisciplinary team approach that includes nurses, non-licensed personnel, therapists, dietitians, physicians, and others with patient contact to participate (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality [AHRQ], 2014).

Statement of Problem

In February 2016, Hill-Rom Medical Technology Company conducted a one-day International PU Prevalence (IPUP) survey in a 160-bed acute care facility in southern California. This survey found that 43% of the patients who developed a HAPU had a Braden score of 15-18 at the time of admission, which is considered low risk. In addition, 29% of those same patients had a score between 19 and 23, considered no risk, upon admission to the hospital. These findings are unexpected because patients who develop HAPUs will typically have lower Braden scores that identify them as high risk for skin breakdown. The most recent score charted on the day of the study for these same patients

with HAPUs were also unexpected with 14% still rated as low risk and 29% rated as no risk. This means that patients who had already developed a HAPU were still being evaluated by nurses as low or no risk.

The facility of study has 15 powered air mattresses, called P500 beds, for use in high-risk patients and patients with PUs. The Hill-Rom study found that 62% of the patients with PUs and 86% of the HAPU patients were not on these specialty beds. With these numbers representing 13 patients with PUs, there were adequate resources for all or most of them to be placed on these advanced surfaces.

The AHRQ (2014), National Guidelines Clearinghouse [NGC] (2012), and National Pressure Ulcer Advisory Panel (NPUAP), European Pressure Ulcer Advisory Panel (EPUAP), and Pan Pacific Ulcer Alliance Panel [PPUAP] (2016) recommend that risk assessments be performed every shift and with any change in condition in acute care settings to assure appropriate interventions. Hill-Rom found that only 55% of the patients had been assessed within the previous 12 hours.

The number of layers between patients and support surfaces should be as limited as possible. With every additional layer underneath a patient, the amount of pressure exerted on the skin surface increases and the ability of specialized mattresses to redistribute the pressure is reduced (Williamson, Lachenbruch, & Vangilder, 2013). Of the patients with HAPUs, 71% had three or more layers beneath them during the prevalence study.

Policies and procedures, new hire and current staff education, and currently utilized competencies are primarily focused on treating PU and other skin injuries in this facility. While treatment of PU is an important aspect of patient care, preserving skin

integrity can prevent the costly complications associated with PU development including increased length of stay, financial burden, and general morbidity and mortality (Aline Arrais Sampaio Santos, Fortes Vitor, Ximenes Teixeira, Pereira de Melo, & VenÃ-cios de Oliveira Lopes, 2012). While many products and devices including foam dressings, heel protector boots and dressings, advanced air mattresses, and skin creams are available for use in the prevention of skin breakdown, information is not available in a central place to guide nurses on when and how to use them. There is a lack of consistent PU prevention protocols available in the practice setting.

Purpose

The purpose of this project was to improve competency in pressure ulcer risk assessment and prevention by 1) developing guidelines for pressure ulcer prevention and 2) providing education based on the guidelines.

The objectives of this project were 1) to evaluate nursing attitudes towards PU prevention to tailor education materials to address areas of concern and barriers and 2) to evaluate compliance with guidelines by measuring appropriateness of Braden scores to patient condition (presence of pressure ulcer), frequency and timeliness of skin/risk assessment, number of layers between patient and surface, and appropriate use of support surfaces.

Supporting Framework

Plan, Do, Study, Act

Edwards Deming's Plan Do Study Act (PDSA) model has been used frequently in healthcare settings for the purposes of quality improvement (Bohnenkamp, Pelton, Rishel, & Kurtin, 2014; Charlton, 2014; Donnelly & Kirk, 2015). The PDSA model was

utilized courtesy of The W. Edwards Deming Institute® to organize and carry out the steps of this project. The four main steps of the PDSA model have been outlined in detail as they pertain to this project (Figure 1).

Plan. Once an area of concern has been identified, the PDSA model can be utilized starting with the plan stage. During the plan stage, objectives are set based on what is trying to be accomplished. According to Donnelly and Kirk (2015), this is when the anticipated answers to the issue should be discussed, short, medium and long-term plans to meet objectives should be set forth, and the way progress is monitored should be outlined in detail. During the plan stage of this project, existing best-practice guidelines for PU prevention were reviewed as were current PU-related policies, procedures, guidelines, education, and competency resources available in the facility of interest. Based on the needs of the facility, aspects of currently published guidelines, along with information from a review of the literature, were identified and adapted into guidelines for PU prevention for the facility. From this, materials were developed for the purposes of communication and education. Educational methods supported by the literature and those currently employed by the facility were reviewed and utilized to deliver education in the most effective way.

All individuals involved in the project, including the wound care nurse, unit director and education director, were a part of the planning stage and roles were defined. Timelines were outlined to assure that the project stayed on track and was completed in the desired time-frame.

Do. The do stage of the project is “where you carry out the change... and record what has happened” (Donnelly & Kirk, 2015, p. 280). This is when the plan will be

carried out, unexpected occurrences will be noted and data will be collected. During this phase, a questionnaire was completed by nursing staff to determine attitudes towards PU prevention and the results were reviewed to determine areas of concern for implementation to assure inclusion of practices that minimize barriers to compliance. Education on the new guidelines was added to the current annual skills day offering as well as the current new staff orientation.

Study. The study phase of the project includes reviewing data that has been collected and discussing the outcomes of the “do” phase. Barriers to implementation will be identified by the team. Results from the attitudes questionnaire were compiled and shared with staff to increase buy-in, reward positive behavior, and improve behavior that does not follow the guidelines. A follow-up Hill-Rom one-day prevalence study was also scheduled to evaluate compliance with guidelines including Braden scores, frequency of assessment, number of layers between a patient and surface, and use of support surfaces.

Act. During the act phase of the PDSA model, the team will review the changes that have occurred and either revise the plan to start another PDSA cycle or decide that the project is ready to be fully implemented (Bohnenkamp et al., 2014). At this time, changes were discussed regarding the way that the guidelines were implemented and how education was offered. A plan for long-term implementation was developed including future prevalence studies, scheduled wound care and education team meetings, and auditing to evaluate proper use of guidelines.

The PDSA model assisted in carrying out the project in an organized fashion that has been employed in many healthcare related projects with great success. It also helped

to establish a plan for long term implementation of the changes to improve quality patient care in the facility.

Figure 1. PDSA Model.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A review of the available literature was conducted in order to answer the following questions: why are PUs a problem?, what are PU risk factors?, what is best practice for PU prevention?, how is PU risk evaluated?, what role does nursing judgment, assessment, and culture play in PU prevention?, are guidelines the best choice for improving patient outcomes?, and what are the aspects of a PU prevention guideline? The search for literature included the following databases: CINAHL, PubMed, EBSCO, Google Scholar, and Cochrane Library. The search terms utilized included the following, in various combinations with various limiters: pressure ulcer, risk factors, cost, burden, prevention, guideline, nursing, attitudes, facilitators, barriers, professional development, education, assessment, culture, and judgment. Articles published in the last ten years (2007-2017) were included based on research that reveals a median of eight years for publication of studies with negative or null results, compared to 4.7 years for significant results (Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions, 2011). Results were not limited geographically but were limited to English language. Articles and sources found in reference lists were reviewed and included as appropriate. Other sources were utilized for a comprehensive understanding of all concepts involved in the project including related unpublished work, wound care specific websites, and the AHRQ toolkit for pressure ulcer prevention in hospitals.

What is a Pressure Ulcer?

The NPUAP (2016) defines a pressure ulcer as “localized damage to the skin and/or underlying soft tissue usually over a bony prominence or related to a medical or other device”. The definition goes on to explain that a pressure ulcer can be an area of

open or intact skin related to pressure and/or shear as well as other patient specific characteristics. The pathophysiology behind pressure ulcers involves both intrinsic factors, which are patient specific characteristics, in combination with extrinsic factors like pressure, friction, and shear (Kruger, Pires, Ngann, Sterling, & Rubayi, 2013). When pressure from the outside exceeds capillary pressure, tissue becomes anoxic, leading to ischemia and eventually necrosis (Kruger et al., 2013).

Prevalence/Incidence

According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC] (2012), prevalence is how many people currently have a condition at a particular time, all cases new and pre-existing, and incidence is the number of people who develop a condition during a particular time. The overall U.S. prevalence for PU in 2009 was 11.9% with a HAPU incidence of 5% (VanGilder, Amlung, Harrison, & Meyer, 2009). Rates have been steadily decreasing since 2006, but continue to be higher than the goal of zero preventable PUs (VanGilder et al., 2009).

Cost/Burden

In the U. S., approximately \$10 billion is spent annually on the care of PUs, many of which are preventable (AHRQ, 2014). Every year there are more than 17,000 PU related lawsuits, second only to wrongful death, and 60,000 deaths directly related to PU (AHRQ, 2014). One study estimated the total cost of PU prevention to be \$54.66 per patient per day, versus a PU treatment cost of \$2,770.54 per patient per day (Padula, Mishra, Makic, & Sullivan, 2011). Beyond the monetary costs associated with the development of PUs, patients are burdened with longer hospital stays and increased overall morbidity and mortality (Lyder et al., 2012). In a population of patients with

recent spinal cord injuries, those who had developed PUs reported decreased levels of activity, difficulty with performing activities of daily living, and decreased quality of life (Lala, Dumont, Leblond, Houghton, & Noreau, 2014).

Risk Factors

The literature identified several individual patient factors associated with increased risk for development of PU including presence of current PU or history of PU, perfusion/circulation issues including diabetes, peripheral vascular disease and tobacco use, increased length of stay, decreased body weight, temperature, hypoalbuminemia, and need for activities of daily living assistance (AHRQ, 2014; Coleman et al., 2013; Mallah, Nassar, & Kurdahi Badr, 2015; National Pressure Ulcer Advisory Panel, European Pressure Ulcer Advisory Panel, & Pan Pacific Pressure Ulcer Alliance, 2014). While some of these risk factors are considered by formal risk assessment tools like the Braden scale, many are not, and so skilled nursing assessment is required.

Assessing Risk

Assessment of risk using formal tools and competent nursing assessment and judgment is the basis of PU prevention guidelines (AHRQ, 2014; NGC, 2012; NPUAP et al., 2014). The AHRQ and NPUAP et al. (2014) recommend the use of a formal tool for assessment and cited the Braden scale as having high validity and reliability as well as being widely utilized.

While validated tools for risk assessment are widely used, they do not replace nursing judgment and assessment for a comprehensive understanding of patient condition (AHRQ, 2014; NPUAP et al., 2014). Patients in critical care and surgical areas rely on nursing assessment, as formal tools are not as successful in predicting risk in these

specialty areas (Mallah et al., 2015). The NPUAP et al. (2014), AHRQ (2014) and NGC (2012) recommend that the initial assessment should take place within eight hours of admission to the hospital, be completed at least once per shift for acute care settings, and be repeated with any change in patient condition such level of care. It is also important to include other licensed and unlicensed staff in monitoring for skin injuries and confirmation of assessment findings (AHRQ, 2014).

Judgment

The concept of nursing judgment includes effective observation and assessment, the ability to interpret findings, knowing how to respond with the correct intervention, and being able to effectively reflect on personal performance in a meaningful way (van Graan, Williams, & Koen, 2016). This means that judgment goes beyond assessment and allows for individualization of care. Physical assessment is a skill taught in nurse training programs, but critical thinking skills vary from nurse to nurse and two nurses may not arrive at the same conclusion given the same information (Choi, Choi, & Kim, 2014). For this reason, a guideline helps to ensure that patients are being provided the best care possible. In the facility of study, the Wound Care and Skin Management Policy calls for an assessment at admission and every shift.

Communication

Standardized documentation and communication of findings is paramount for identifying patients at risk and recognizing changes in risk throughout hospitalization (AHRQ, 2014; NGC, 2012; NPUAP et al., 2014). A performance improvement project conducted at four hospitals found that none of the facilities routinely included PU risk in handoff communication between nurses, nursing assistants, physicians, or transporters

(Jankowski & Nadzam, 2011). The facility of study does not currently include PU risk scores on the handoff communication forms or routinely during change of shift reports. The addition of this item will help communicate risk between health care professionals to ensure proper intervention and improved preventative practices.

Braden

The Braden scale takes extrinsic factors into account when used to evaluate a patient's individual risk for skin breakdown. The six areas of measurement in the Braden Scale for Predicting Pressure Sore Risk are Sensory Perception, Moisture, Activity, Mobility, Nutrition, and Friction and Sheer (Appendix A). A minimum score of six and a maximum score of 23 are possible and the levels of risk are illustrated in Table 1 (Braden & Maklebust, 2005). The Braden scale is the tool currently used by the facility of study.

Table 1

Braden Risk Levels

Braden Score	Risk Category
19 to 23	Not at risk
15 to 18	Mild risk
13 to 14	Moderate risk
10 to 12	High risk
9 or lower	Very high risk

The risk categories were revised in the 1990s to include 18 and below as at-risk scores where previously the cut off had been 16 (Braden & Maklebust, 2005). Thanks to wide use of the Braden scale throughout the world, a considerable amount of research has been conducted with regards to the validity and reliability measuring the scale's

sensitivity ranges from 70% to 100% and specificity ranges between 64% and 90% (Braden & Maklebust, 2005).

In a study of nurses' interpretations of the Braden score elements, researchers found large variations in the way the vague patient characteristics were understood from nurse to nurse (Choi et al., 2014). For example, under the measure of moisture two nurses may not agree about whether a patient is 'occasionally moist' or 'very moist'. These variations in interpretation can allow for at risk patients to be miscategorized. At the facility of study the only current trigger to recommend a wound care nurse consult and skin management care plan is a Braden score less than 18. In the case of patients who are at risk for PU and improperly categorized, preventative care and appropriate interventions can be missed, leading to higher risk for PU development. Prevention of PUs requires competent nursing assessment, but literature shows that nurses rely heavily on prior experience when making decisions about which patients are at risk and what interventions to employ (Samuriwo & Dowding, 2014). Relying on experience instead of evidence causes care to be inconsistent and potentially harmful. The implementation of evidence-based guidelines for PU prevention will give staff the resources to appropriately use assessment, judgment, validated tools, and best practice to improve competence and consistency of care.

Nursing Considerations

Culture

Facility- and unit-specific culture can facilitate or block successful changes in practice. Staffing issues, knowledge deficits, lack of experienced nurses, and confusion between roles of various staff members can affect whether guidelines are followed and

interventions are employed (Dilie & Mengistu, 2015; Waugh, 2014). When nurses are busy and do not feel supported, they report that attending to other duties took priority over skin assessment (Samuriwo & Dowding, 2014). The need for established routines for PU prevention and consistent communication between providers about individual patient risks are necessary components of a facility culture supportive of PU prevention (Jankowski & Nadzam, 2011; Waugh, 2014). Chaboyer and Gillespie (2014) suggested that involving patients in PU prevention can reduce the workload of nurses by assigning some responsibility for prevention strategies to the patients and family members as appropriate. If prevention strategies are to be successfully implemented, staff and patients need to understand why prevention is necessary and what can happen if strategies are not carried out (Chaboyer & Gillespie, 2014; Sving, Fredriksson, Gunningberg, & Mamhidir, 2016). This would require education and demonstration upfront, but has the potential to take some of the workload from the nurse in the end while empowering patients to become more involved in their own care.

Affecting behavior and securing buy-in by any group of people in a lasting and meaningful way, requires input and feedback (Charlton, 2014; Sving et al., 2016). Despite education and follow-up, nurses are not always compliant with facility guidelines (Baumgarten et al., 2010; Cason, Tyner, Saunders, & Broome, 2007; Ludikhuizen, de Jonge, & Goossens, 2011; Revello & Fields, 2012). Doing meaningful work, having responsibility for outcomes, and being aware of how they are performing were found to be necessary factors in motivating nurses (Toode, Routasalo, Helminen, & Suominen, 2014). Including staff in the discussion of outcomes will help to make them aware of

their contributions and performance and make the work of PU prevention more meaningful.

Nursing Attitudes

An important factor to consider in examining factors related to any clinical issue is attitude. Nurses' attitudes toward PU prevention have been studied in different settings around the world, revealing that the likelihood of prevention measures being carried out relies heavily on how nurses feel about those measures (Källman & Suserud, 2009; Moore & Price, 2004; Strand & Lindgren, 2010). If nurses believe that PU prevalence is decreasing, that PU prevention is time consuming, or that most PUs are not preventable, they are less likely to adhere to PU prevention guidelines (AHRQ, 2014; Källman & Suserud, 2009; Moore & Price, 2004; Strand & Lindgren, 2010). Before implementing any project, staff attitudes should be evaluated to identify areas of need for education and further exploration.

Prevention Guidelines

Bundles and PU prevention guidelines have consistently proven effective at reducing PU incidence in studies worldwide (Armour-Burton, Fields, Outlaw, & Deleon, 2013; Barker et al., 2013; Crawford, Corbett, & Zuniga, 2014; Mallah et al., 2015; Sving et al., 2016; Tashman, 2016; Tayyib, Coyer, & Lewis, 2015). There is a great deal of agreement about the general strategies necessary to prevent PU development: risk assessment, skin care, nutritional factors, mobility and positioning, and education (AHRQ, 2014; NGC, 2012; NPUAP et al., 2014). Each was explored for potential inclusion.

Skin Care

Skin care for all patients is necessary to identify high risk patients and prevent the development of PU. Skin should be inspected at admission and every day during hospitalization, with a focus on high pressure areas such as the sacrum and heels (AHRQ, 2014; NGC, 2012; NPUAP et al., 2014). Timely cleansing after episodes of incontinence is vital to maintaining skin integrity (NPUAP, 2014). Moisture weakens the skin making it more susceptible to pressure and shear, which, in combination with other factors, can lead to PU development (Beeckman, Van Lancker, Van Hecke, & Verhaeghe, 2014). The use of diapers has been associated with higher risk for PU development and many successful prevention programs have included no diaper policies (Armour-Burton et al., 2013; Crawford et al., 2014; Pieper, 2013). The use of massage for prevention of PU is no longer advised because this practice increases pressure on the tissue rather than relieving pressure as many had previously believed (Pieper, 2013).

Skin Care Products

Many guidelines call for the prophylactic use of skin cleansers and creams for protection and prevention of skin break down and the implementation of a guideline that provides recommendations for use can increase compliance (AHRQ, 2014; NGC, 2012; NPUAP et al., 2014). The data supporting the use of creams is not conclusive, but shows some possible positive effects when used along with the other protective interventions included in PU prevention guidelines (Chaboyer & Gillespie, 2014; Mallah et al., 2015; Qaseem, Mir, Starkey, & Denberg, 2015).

Nutritional Factors

Nutritional factors are closely associated to risk for PU development and should be taken into consideration when developing guidelines (AHRQ, 2014; NGC, 2012; NPUAP et al., 2014). Intake and output measurements, frequent weight assessments, and appropriate referral to a registered dietitian as well as vitamin and dietary supplementation are all aspects of care that should be included (AHRQ, 2014; NGC, 2012; NPUAP et al., 2014). Poor intake and overall poor nutrition are both factors that increase likelihood of PU development as well as complicate healing processes (Posthauer, Banks, Dorner, & Schols, 2015). Protein, Vitamin C, and Zinc are important nutrients that may be lacking in a patient with decreased intake, recent weight loss, difficulty chewing and/or swallowing, or acute illness or stress (Posthauer et al., 2015). When poor nutritional status is suspected, a registered dietitian should be consulted (AHRQ, 2014; NPUAP et al., 2014; Posthauer et al., 2015).

Mobility and Positioning

Routine repositioning of chair and bed bound patients and early mobilization of ambulatory patients are important strategies for the prevention of PU development (AHRQ, 2014; NGC, 2012; NPUAP et al., 2014). A Cochrane review found no randomized controlled trials or controlled clinical trials that evaluated turning to prevent pressure ulcer development, although there were anecdotal and expert recommendations to do so across the board (Moore & Cowman, 2015). Many guidelines advise a turning schedule of every two hours, while others point out that specific patient characteristics like temperature, moisture, and overall patient condition may necessitate more frequent repositioning (AHRQ, 2014; NGC, 2012; NPUAP et al., 2014). Despite these consistent

suggestions, one study found that repositioning was the intervention that nurses carried out the least often in preventing PU, likely because of a lack of time and assistance (Mallah et al., 2015). Patients should be positioned at a 30-degree angle, with heels elevated off the mattress and not on an area of compromised skin (AHRQ, 2014; NGC, 2012; NPUAP et al., 2014).

Mattresses and Devices

While the appropriate utilization of pressure relieving devices such as heel protectors, chair cushions, waffle boots and overlays, and specialized mattresses is known to aid in the prevention of pressure ulcers, these devices are greatly under used in the clinical setting (Barker et al., 2013; Niederhauser et al., 2012). Specialized mattresses and support surface help to redistribute pressure by increasing contact surface area and controlling temperature, however patients on specialized mattresses still need to be repositioned at appropriate intervals (Moore, Haynes, & Callaghan, 2014; NPUAP et al. 2014). Cushions should be used in wheelchairs and chairs, with seated patients repositioned at least every hour (NPUAP et al., 2014). Heel protectors, cushions, and boots work to lift high-risk areas like the heels off of the mattress and redistributing weight when patients are seated (NPUAP et al. 2014). A guideline that directs when patients should be treated with these preventative and supportive measures may serve to increase compliance with use when a patient is identified as high-risk.

Education

The final piece of any PU prevention guideline is education of both the patient and family members and the staff. Guidelines cannot be successful unless the individuals involved are aware of them and educated on how to implement them. The AHRQ (2014),

NGC (2012), and NPUAP et al. (2014) recommend that patients and families be educated on the risks for PU development and how to prevent PU. A survey of acute care patients revealed that they were interested in being involved in PU prevention, but that only 37% had been provided education related to PU prevention (McInnes, Chaboyer, Murray, Allen, & Jones, 2014). The use of formal education on guidelines, policies, skin care products and pressure relieving devices as well as the inclusion of this education in new hire orientation is supported by the literature (Niederhauser et al., 2012). This was found to be more effective in relation to long-term retention and competency than more unstructured, informal ways of conveying the information (Armour-Burton et al., 2013).

METHODS

The purpose of this Quality Improvement (QI) project was to develop and implement best practice guidelines for prevention of PUs. This project included examination of nursing attitudes towards PU prevention, care guideline development and implementation and educational plan design and delivery. The institutional review board was consulted and approvals were obtained from both the facility and the university to ensure ethical treatment of all information included in this QI project. There was little risk to participants as no identifiable information was collected.

Stakeholders, comprised of the wound care nurse, education director, unit managers, and staff, were included in decisions about guideline development, educational offerings, and dissemination of findings. An information technology (IT) staff member responsible for the facility's electronic health record (EHR) was also consulted to explore the possibility of adding patient risk information (Braden score and risk category) to communication forms. It was also recommended to make changes to EHR to allow nurses to classify patients as high-risk for PU development based on additional assessment factors besides the Braden score.

Setting

The setting for the project was a 160-bed acute care community hospital in Riverside County, CA. The facility includes medical surgical, telemetry, progressive care, intensive care, pediatrics, emergency and obstetrics units.

Sample

A convenience sample of registered nurses (RNs) working in the medical surgical, progressive care, and intensive care units were included in the questionnaire portion of

the project. All RNs in the facility received formal education on PU prevention and the newly created guidelines during the mandatory new hire orientation and annual skills day, receiving a copy of the guidelines and reviewing a poster containing data and rationale with the wound care nurse.

Measures

The first measure collected was the ‘Clinical Staff Attitudes Toward Pressure Ulcer Prevention’ questionnaire (Appendix B); it was used and reprinted with permission (AHRQ, 2014). Demographics of age, sex, number of years as an RN and highest level of education were also collected. A follow-up one-day prevalence study was performed to reevaluate Braden scores, frequency of assessment, layers of linen, and support surface use to measure compliance to the guidelines. IT was consulted to evaluate if the number of times a patient was placed in the high-risk category based on other assessment findings versus Braden score can be audited once the option is added to nurse charting.

Procedures

Attitudes Questionnaire

Questionnaires were distributed to nurses on duty during two different days shifts and two different night shifts (one weekend and one weekday each, over two weeks) to obtain as many responses as possible, along with a blank envelop to preserve anonymity. Nurses were informed that participation was optional and no identifying information was collected. All data were entered into Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 24 for analysis.

Guideline Development

Guidelines were developed by adapting the AHRQ (2014), NGC (2012), and NPUAP et al. (2014) guidelines to meet the specific needs of the facility of study with input from the wound care nurse and director of education. There is significant agreement between these guidelines and all major areas were covered in the adapted guidelines prepared for the facility.

Educational Offerings

Once the best practice guidelines were developed, educational materials were created for use during the existing new hire orientations and annual skills day offerings. All clinical staff also received a copy of the guidelines and educational materials in preparation for competency. Posters and flyers were posted in high traffic areas on all units for nurses to review and to keep the new material fresh in everyone's minds. The NPUAP et al. (2014) has developed a competency-based curriculum for PU prevention, which details educational objectives, content, topics, teaching methods, and possible references which were reviewed when creating the educational component of the QI project. Facility specific needs were also discussed with the wound care nurse and director of education for inclusion including the frequency of assessment, two nurse skin checks and specific care plans available in the EHR.

Table 2

Timeline of QI Project

09/2017	10/2017	11/2017	02/2018
Attitude Questionnaire & Development of Guidelines	Development of Educational Materials and Handouts	Implementation of Education	Hill-Rom Follow-up Study

RESULTS

The purpose of this project was to improve competency in pressure ulcer risk assessment and prevention by 1) developing guidelines for pressure ulcer prevention and 2) providing education based on the guidelines. The final product of this quality improvement project was a manuscript to be submitted for publication in the journal *Wounds International*. This manuscript is Appendix A. Wounds International's author guidelines can be found in Appendix B. The project was also part of a poster presentation at California State University, Fullerton's Upsilon Beta Sigma Theta Tau International Nursing Honor Society's Induction of New Members on April 21, 2018. Final guidelines can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Guidelines

DISCUSSION

The results of this quality improvement project confirm the value of formalized guidelines and agency-wide education in providing high quality, evidence-based patient care. The introduction of these prevention guidelines and the educational offerings that accompanied them not only contributed to improved IPUP survey outcomes, but also led to more engaged staff. The teams that carried out the survey noted that staff were aware of what was going on during the survey and knowledgeable, in contrast to previous years.

The two areas with the greatest improvement after the implementation of guidelines were timeliness of Braden assessment and layers of linens. In 2016 only 55% of patients had a Braden score documented in the previous 12 hours, which is facility policy. The 2018 IPUP found that 90% of patients had Braden scores within the 12-hour window. In 2016 only 29% of HAPU patients were found to have the recommended two or fewer layers of linen between skin and surface. This jumped to 100% in 2018. Among all patients surveyed (HAPU, PU and intact skin), only two were found to have more than two layers- both with three. This is a significant improvement that will help to prevent the development of PUs in the facility. It is possible that the nurses were not aware of the facility policies, or that the easy access to information (posted guidelines and recent education) led to the increases in these areas.

Improvements were also found in the correlation between Braden score and actual risk for HAPU development. The percentage of HAPU patients with low or no risk scores on admission decreased from 72% in 2016 to 60% in 2018. There was also a decrease in the percentage of HAPU patients with low or no risk scores on the day of the study, from 43% in 2016 to 20% in 2018. These numbers indicate that the Braden scores are more

reflective of the patients' actual risk for skin breakdown. There continues to be room for improvement in these areas. Results are seen in Table 3.

Table 3

2016/2018 IPUP Survey Results Comparison

Survey Demographics	2016	2018
Total # of Patients	70	73
# of PU Patients	13	14
# of HAPU Patients	7	5
Area of Interest	2016	2018
HAPU pts with low/no risk Braden scores on admission	72%	60%
HAPU pts with day of study low/no risk Braden scores	43%	20%
% of pts with a Braden assessment documented within 12 hours	55%	90%
% of HAPU pts with recommended 2 or fewer layers between pt and surface	29%	100%
Use of P500 bed for HAPU pts	14%	0%

The only area that did not see improvement was the use of support surfaces, specifically the P500 bed, for HAPU patients. Only 14% (n=1) of HAPU patients in 2016 were placed on a P500 bed, and 0% of HAPU patients were on P500 beds in 2018. Even though these are small numbers, this is a critical part of preventing PU development and deterioration. It is possible that the time and manpower needed to move a patient from one bed to another is a deterrent, as well as the high census and lack of empty beds to move patients around. This area deserves increased focus and education moving forward.

A competency evaluation test was developed using the AHRQ (2014) "Preventing PUs in Hospitals" toolkit, which offers a PU prevention knowledge evaluation tool for use in acute care settings. Additional, facility-specific questions were added in order to

measure competency of the new guidelines and general PU risk and prevention factors. This competency was not approved for use in time for this project but is planned for inclusion in skills day and new staff orientation in the future. This tool would have provided additional information about areas that need further education and overall nursing staff competency related to PU prevention.

Recommendations

Recommendations for the future include continuing to provide a copy of the PU prevention guidelines to all nurses during orientation as well as during annual skills day training. Starting in 2018, the PU prevention competency will be added to the skills day packet. Annual prevalence surveys will continue in order to track progress, and guidelines will be reviewed and revised as needed by the facility. It has also been recommended that the computerized charting system be modified to: 1) allow nurses to identify a patient as high risk for PU based on factors outside of the Braden score, and 2) include the patient's Braden score and risk category on the shift report. These changes will need to be approved on a corporate level before implementation.

The appropriate use of support surfaces will be stressed moving forward, including education and audits by the charge nurses and wound care nurse. This area will continue to be monitored in future IPUP surveys.

Implications for Practice

The results of this project have implications for practice in both the facility of study and the wider world of nursing. While changes have already occurred at the facility during this project, the results support continued evaluation and change of current protocol. Positive results also have the ability to stimulate interest in additional quality

improvement projects in the future. There are also benefits related to staff morale. When staff are able to see the positive results of hard work and evidence-based practice, they are more likely to be engaged in future projects (Fleischer, Semenic, Ritchie, Richer & Denis, 2016).

The profession of nursing can benefit from positive results in patient care areas. This project adds to support for the use of guidelines to help provide evidence based, high quality patient care (Anderson et al., 2014). PU prevention guidelines will help to ensure that patients are being provided the most appropriate interventions based on research and evidence and that nurses will have support and direction in their patient care.

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APPENDIX A

MANUSCRIPT FOR WOUNDS INTERNATIONAL

Development of Guidelines for Pressure Ulcer Prevention

Summary

Evidence based pressure ulcer (PU) prevention guidelines were developed for a Southern California regional medical center following concerning one-day prevalence survey results. Previous focus had been placed on treatment of PUs with little education and policy related to prevention. After familiarizing staff with the new guidelines and providing education, the results of the follow-up one-day prevalence study were significantly improved in most areas of interest.

Introduction

The development of hospital acquired pressure ulcers (HAPU) has been linked to increased rates of readmission (within 30 days of discharge), increased in-hospital mortality rates, and an increase in mortality rates within 30 days of discharge (Lyder et al., 2012). The average cost to heal a pressure ulcer (PU) can range significantly, depending on severity, from hundreds of dollars to over one hundred thousand dollars (Meddings et al., 2015). According to Meddings et al (2015), reimbursement for hospitalization was decreased by “an average of \$5,604 per discharge” for Stage III or IV HAPUs (p. 1409).

In 2016, a Hill Rom International Pressure Ulcer Prevalence (IPUP) Survey was conducted and identified several areas of concern:

- Patients who had developed HAPUs had low/no risk Braden scores on admission
- Patients still had low/no risk Braden scores even after development of HAPU
- The facility’s support surfaces (including advanced air mattresses [P500]) were not being utilized appropriately
- Many patients had not had a Braden assessment documented in the previous 12 hours, despite facility policy requiring assessment every shift
- The number of linens between patients and the support surface they were placed on was higher than the recommendation of two or less

The Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality [AHRQ] (2014), National Guidelines Clearinghouse [NGC] (2012), National Pressure Ulcer Advisory Panel (NPUAP), European Pressure Ulcer Advisory Panel (EPUAP), and Pan Pacific Ulcer Alliance Panel (PPUAP) (2016) agree on the importance of having PU prevention guidelines in place and make recommendations on the areas that should be included.

Purpose of Project

The purpose of this project was to improve competency in pressure ulcer risk assessment and prevention by:

- developing guidelines for pressure ulcer prevention and

- providing education and a competency evaluation tool based on the guidelines.

The objectives of this project were:

- to evaluate nursing attitudes towards PU prevention to tailor education materials to address areas of concern and barriers and
- to evaluate compliance with guidelines by measuring appropriateness of Braden scores to patient condition (presence of pressure ulcer), frequency and timeliness of skin/risk assessment, number of layers between patient and surface and appropriate use of support surfaces.

Methods

Edwards Deming's Plan Do Study Act (PDSA) model has been used frequently in healthcare settings for the purposes of quality improvement (Bohnenkamp, Pelton, Rishel, & Kurtin, 2014; Charlton, 2014; Donnelly & Kirk, 2015). The PDSA model was utilized courtesy of The W. Edwards Deming Institute® to organize and carry out the steps of this project.

Collaboration

This project was completed in collaboration with the facility wound care coordinator and the director of education. Current policies and educational materials were reviewed and facility specific needs were discussed throughout the process. Facility administration was also supportive of the project and provided feedback and approval.

Facility Guideline Development

The following areas were included in the new facility guidelines (figure 1):

- **Risk assessment**- Risk assessment is the basis of all PU prevention guidelines, and a formal tool is recommended. The facility currently uses the Braden scale, which has been cited as having high validity and reliability. (AHRQ, 2014; NGC, 2012; NPUAP et al., 2014)
- **Skin care**- Skin care and inspection allow for identification of high risk patients as well as prevention of skin breakdown. This area includes management of moisture and use of skin care products. (AHRQ, 2014; Beeckman, Van Lancker, Van Hecke, & Verhaeghe, 2014; NGC, 2012; NPUAP et al., 2014)
- **Nutritional factors**- Poor nutrition can increase likelihood of PU development as well as complicate the healing process. Collaboration with a registered dietitian is recommended. (AHRQ, 2014; NGC, 2012; NPUAP et al., 2014; Posthauer, Banks, Dorner, & Schols, 2015)
- **Mobility and positioning**- Repositioning and mobilization of patients is vital in prevention of PU. Patient specific factors (moisture, temperature, overall condition) may necessitate more frequent repositioning. This area also included the use of appropriate support surfaces and other pressure relieving devices (advanced air mattresses, heel protectors etc.). (AHRQ, 2014; Barker et al., 2013; Moore & Cowman, 2015; NGC, 2012; Niederhauser et al., 2012; NPUAP et al., 2014)

- **Education-** Education of staff, patients and family members regarding PU prevention strategies helps ensure compliance and involves patients in their own care in a meaningful way. It can also help take some of the burden off of staff. (AHRQ, 2014; McInnes, Chaboyer, Murray, Allen, & Jones, 2014; NGC, 2012; NPUAP et al., 2014)

Nursing Attitudes

Once the review of literature was completed and the guidelines had been developed, the nurses were invited to participate in a questionnaire regarding their attitudes toward PU prevention. Nurses' attitudes toward PU prevention have been studied in different settings around the world, revealing that the likelihood of prevention measures being carried out relies heavily on how nurses feel about those measures (Källman & Suserud, 2009; Moore & Price, 2004; Strand & Lindgren, 2010). If nurses believe that PU prevalence is decreasing, that PU prevention is time consuming, or that most PUs are not preventable, or if they are less interested in PU prevention than other aspects of nursing care, they are less likely to adhere to PU prevention guidelines (AHRQ, 2014; Källman & Suserud, 2009; Moore & Price, 2004; Strand & Lindgren, 2010). The questionnaire revealed that 25% of the nurses felt that PU prevention was time consuming and 93% believed that treatment was NOT priority over prevention. 15% of the nurse respondents did not agree that most PUs can be avoided. While this is a small number (n=8 out of 54 total), it is concerning. The results of this questionnaire helped to guide the educational offerings in the facility.

Educational Offerings

The NPUAP et al. (2014) has developed a competency-based curriculum for PU prevention, which details educational objectives, content, topics, teaching methods, and possible references which was reviewed when creating the educational component of this QI project. Once the best practice guidelines were developed, educational materials were created for use during the existing new hire orientations and annual skills day offering for current employees. All clinical staff received a copy of the guidelines and educational materials in preparation for the follow-up IPUP survey. Flyers illustrating the new PU prevention guidelines were posted in high traffic areas (figure 1) and a poster outlining the research behind the development of the guidelines, results of the attitudes questionnaire, previous IPUP results, and areas of focus for improvement was presented and the annual skills day. Two copies of this poster were prepared for the wound care nurse for posting in staff breakrooms on a rotating schedule

IPUP Survey

In February 2016, a Hill Rom IPUP survey was conducted at the facility in the ICU, PCU and MS units. At that time, there were 70 patients surveyed in total, including 13 PU patients- seven of which had HAPUs (Table 1).

In February 2018, a follow-up Hill Rom IPUP survey was conducted using the same units (ICU, PCU and MS) and, in all, 73 patients were included. Of those 73 patients, there were 14 patients with PUs- five of which had HAPUs.

On the day of the survey, a four-person team including an RN lead and three fourth-semester nursing students was sent to each unit included in the survey (ICU, PCU and MS). The RNs and students received training on how to assess the patients for the IPUP survey and how to fill in the standardized scantron forms. Much of the demographic information had been completed by trained, night shift supervisors the morning of the survey.

IPUP Results

One of the areas of interest for the IPUP survey was the appropriateness of Braden scores for patients who either developed or had HAPUs. In 2016, 72% of patients who went on to develop HAPUs were assessed to be low or no risk at the time of admission. This number went down to 60% for 2018. Another concern identified following the IPUP survey was that, in 2016, 43% of these patients were still receiving Braden scores that placed them in the low or no risk categories even after HAPU development. In 2018, only 20% were rated low risk and none of them were in the no risk category.

In 2016, only 55% of the patients surveyed had a Braden assessment in the previous 12 hours. The 2018 IPUP showed 90% of patients overall had a Braden score entered within the previous 12 hours.

The survey also recorded the number of layers between a patient's skin and the support surface. In 2016, 71% of the HAPU patients had three or more layers. None of the HAPU patients in 2018 had more than two layers between their skin and the support surface. In fact, 97% of the patients surveyed in 2018 (HAPU, PU and otherwise) were found to have two layers or less, up from 48% in 2016.

The support surface in use for HAPU patients was also reviewed. In 2016, only 14% of HAPU patients (n=1) were placed on powered air mattresses called P500. None of the 2018 HAPU patients were found on these mattresses.

These results can be seen in Table 1.

Discussion

Overall, an improvement can be seen in the IPUP results from 2016 to 2018. It is clear that the Braden scores are more closely correlating to actual risk for skin breakdown, although there is still room for improvement in this area. The timeliness of Braden assessment was a significant improvement, increasing from 55% to 90%. The area of greatest improvement was that of layers between patient and support surface. There were only two patients surveyed that had more than two layers of linen, both having three. Knowing that each layer adds to the pressure on a patient's skin and risk for PU development, this is a positive change.

The area of most concern is the use of appropriate support surface. Only one of the HAPU patients in 2016 was found on a P500 bed, and none of the HAPU patients in 2018 were on a P500. While there has been a lot of education on all of these areas of prevention, this was the only one with no improvement. It is possible that this could be due to high census (less empty beds) and the difficulty associated with moving patients from one bed to another. Not only is it physically demanding to move a patient from one

bed to another, it also requires time and assistance from other staff. This will be an area of focus moving forward, and unit directors have been made included in dissemination of these results.

Implications

It is clear when reviewing the results of the 2018 IPUP survey that the introduction of PU prevention guidelines, along with education, has improved patient care at the facility. Braden scores are more closely correlating with actual risk for PU development, patients are being assessed more frequently, and there has been an overall reduction in the number of layers between the patient and the support surface in use. The results of this project have implications for practice in both the facility of study and the wider world of nursing. While changes have already occurred at the facility during this project, the results support continued evaluation and change of current protocol. Positive results also have the ability to stimulate interest in additional quality improvement projects in the future. There are also benefits related to staff morale. When staff are able to see the positive results of hard work and evidence-based practice, they are more likely to be engaged in future projects (Fleiszer, Semenic, Ritchie, Richer & Denis, 2016).

The field of nursing can benefit from positive results in patient care areas. This project adds to support for the use of guidelines to help provide evidence based, high quality patient care (Anderson et al., 2014). Guidelines will help to ensure that patients are being provided the most appropriate interventions based on research and evidence and that nurses will have support and direction in their patient care.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The development of guidelines for PU prevention and the education of staff have shown to be beneficial when comparing IPUP survey results from 2016 and 2018. While there have been positive changes, there have also been areas identified that still need work. Moving forward, it will be imperative that education and focus on following guidelines continue in order to maintain the positive changes improve the areas with room for improvement. The education will continue to be provided to new staff as well as current staff at mandatory, annual skills day. The guidelines continue to be prominently placed in common areas and the IPUP surveys will be done annually to gauge outcomes.

There also remains a recommendation for the facility to allow nurses to identify a patient as “at-risk” for PU, regardless of the Braden score, based on nursing assessment. The use of formal assessment tools is not meant to replace nursing assessment, and this would allow the nursing assessment to be included in identification of patients with other risk factors such as peripheral vascular disease, tobacco use, diabetes and history of PU (AHRQ, 2014; Coleman et al., 2013; Mallah, Nassar, & Kurdahi Badr, 2015; NPUAP, EPUAP, & Pan Pacific Pressure Ulcer Alliance, 2014). There has been discussion of including the Braden score and risk level on the shift report sheet. This would allow for easy communication of risk during hand off report between nurses, which the literature shows may not be happening (Jankowski & Nadzam, 2011). These changes have been discussed and decisions must be made at a corporate level.

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Figure 1

Table 1

Table 1: 2016/2018 IPUP Results Comparison		
Survey Demographics	2016	2018
Total # of Patients	70	73
# of PU Patients	13	14
# of HAPU Patients	7	5
Area of interest	2016	2018
HAPU patients (pts) with low/no risk Braden scores on admission	72%	60%
HAPU pts on day of study with low/no risk Braden scores	43%	20%
% of pts with a Braden assessment documented within 12 hours	55%	90%
% of HAPU pts with recommended 2 or fewer layers between pt and surface	29%	100%
Use of P500 bed for HAPU pts	14%	0%

APPENDIX B

WOUNDS INTERNATIONAL AUTHOR GUIDELINES

AUTHOR GUIDELINES FOR *WOUNDS INTERNATIONAL*

Wounds International is a quarterly online practice-based journal for health care professionals who wish to keep up to date and fully informed about the clinical, practical, educational, research and policy aspects of wound care world wide.

If you are interested in submitting an article for *Wounds International*, please read the author guidelines below. If you have any questions or concerns, contact the editor Adam Bushby (abushby@omniamed.com) The article should be unpublished and not submitted for publication elsewhere. *Wounds International* requires authors to grant an exclusive licence to help ensure international protection against infringement of copyright for content it publishes. All papers are published subject to peer review.

Articles published in the journal will normally fall into the following categories. Any necessity for shorter or longer articles should be discussed with the editor:

- **Editorial and Opinion:** essays that discuss or report on current issues in wound care. You may use it as a platform to debate or highlight change or controversial issues. Word count: **650–1300 words**.
- **Clinical Practice:** evidence-based articles, which allow the author(s) to discuss and raise awareness of important topics relating to wound care. A clinical practice article should include the latest evidence-based guidelines/research relating to the topic. Articles should contain an introduction/abstract, conclusions, making use of bullet points where necessary. The main body of the article should be structured by making use of sub-headings, figures and tables and boxes as appropriate. Word count: **2000–2500 words**. This section also contains Top Ten Tips on specific topics.
- **Case Reports:** Provide honest accounts of care given and reflect different practices around the world. Clinicians are invited to submit interesting case reports based on an individual patient (ensuring consent and confidentiality). These should provide a clear rationale for the care given and should be written in an academic style. Relevant references and photographs should be provided. Word count: **1000–2000 words**. Reference limit: 50. This section may also contain a patient story, in which the voice is not that of the clinician but the patient, retelling his or her wound healing journey. Clinical comments are sometimes sought to put the story in its clinical context.
- **Product and Technology:** Reports on new technology, product reviews and evaluations. **1000–2000 words**. Reference limit: 50.
- **Update:** Each issue contains a research round up (Wound Digest), which summarises the most important papers published recently. The papers are rated according to readability, applicability to daily practice and impact. This section may also contain Reviews on recently published guidelines or any other news or updates relevant to wound care.

Comments are sometimes sought from authors or well-known figures in wound care on papers that present particularly interesting or potentially controversial results.

General presentation guidance

All articles should be submitted in 12-point font and at least 1.5 or double line spacing, formatted for A4 paper, and all pages should be numbered.

A separate page for author details, which contains

- The names of the authors
- Institutional affiliation of each author
- Full details of each author's current appointment.
- Name, postal and e-mail address and contact telephone number of the author responsible for correspondence.

Article pages

The article should contain the following key elements:

Title — a descriptive and interest-provoking heading for the article.

Summary — a stand-alone paragraph of no more than 60-100 words giving a brief outline of the content of the article.

Introduction — designed to develop readers' interest in the article and tell them something about the way it is handled. It should also state the main question or questions that the article sets out to answer where applicable.

Body of text — headings can help to provide structure to your article and guide the reader to particular sections.

Conclusions and recommendations — these should be succinct and logically ordered. Identify gaps in knowledge and suggest future initiatives.

Tables and figures — appropriate and clear tables and figures can be a great help to readers. Indicate clearly which point they illustrate in the main text but insert them separately at the end of your article.

It is the author's responsibility to obtain written permission from the copyright holder to reproduce figures, tables, or artwork from other journals or books before submitting the article. It is usually the publisher, not the author, who owns copyright. Permission will be acknowledged at the end of the printed article.

REFERENCES (HARVARD)

In the main text:

1. The Harvard system involves using the name and the year of the reference in the text:

As Black and White (1987) have shown...

As already reported (Black and White, 1987)...

2. For three or more authors, print the author's name followed by et al:

As Black et al (1987) have shown...

Note: 'et al' should never be used to represent one name. Therefore Black et al is acceptable when et al refers to White and Green (i.e. the three authors are Black White

and Green), but it is not acceptable when it refers to only White (i.e. when there are only two authors: Black and White).

3. When several references are cited simultaneously the order should be chronological rather than alphabetical:

As several references have shown (White and Green, 1988; Black and Green, 1993) ...

In the reference list at the end of the article:

a. Arrange references alphabetically by first author's name.

b. Print the names and initials of all authors for references with four or fewer authors:

Black B, Green G (1965) ...

Black B, White W (1963) ...

Black B, White W, Green G, Brown B (1973) ...

Black B, Green G, Tan T (1974) ...

Black B, Abel C, Tan T (1975) ...

The last three references in the above list are in chronological order as they are all cited as Black et al in the text. For five or more authors print the first three and add 'et al' — these references are arranged chronologically:

Black B, White W, Green G et al (1973) ...

Black B, Green G, Tan T et al (1974) ...

Black B, Abel C, Tan T (1975) ...

Use semicolons if referring to more than one article by the same author:

Black et al, 1973; 1974; 1975 ...

The references in the above list are also in chronological order as they too are cited as Black et al in the text.

4. For two or more papers published by the same author(s) in the same year, add the letters a, b, c etc. to the date, (e.g. Black, 1986a).

5. The sequence for a standard journal article is: author(s); year; title; journal; volume number; issue number; first and last page numbers. Note that there is no comma between name and initials; no stop after et al, nor a comma before et al; the journal title should be in italics and abbreviated as in PubMed (no stops); volume number should be bold; issue number can be included; inclusive pagination can be abbreviated by deleting the number that is repeated, e.g. 42–6. The layout and punctuation are:

Smith B, Abel CH (1987) Sexual hypersensitivity. *Br J Nurs* 1(4): 40–6

Where no author is given for a paper, use Anonymous.

Supplements should be referenced as such (usually indicated after the title of the article

and/or with the Vol/Issue no).

Where a reference is to a letter in a journal, this is indicated as follows:

Green GH (1976) Pulmonary complications of AIDS (Letter). *Br J Hosp Med* 38: 461

6. The sequence, layout and punctuation for books are:

Personal author:

Ellis H (1980) *Lecture Notes on Psychiatry*. 5th edn. Blackwell, Oxford

Editor:

Scott H, Brown B, eds (1973) *Histocompatibility Testing*. Vol 5. Raven Press, New York: 418–19

Chapter in book:

Samuels B (1979) Pulmonary complications of AIDS. In: Rand A, Long B. eds, *Management of AIDS*. Butterworths, London: 387–95

Book titles have initial caps for key words but chapter titles are set in upper and lower case.

Book titles are italicized, chapter titles are not.

7. Papers that have been submitted for publication but have not yet been accepted are not acceptable as references. They should only be cited in the text as 'unpublished observations': (XY Smith, unpublished observations, with or without a date when it will be published). Similarly, 'personal communication' should be inserted in the text in brackets.

8. Papers that have been accepted for publication but have not yet been published may be included in the reference list:

Abel HL (1993) *Endometriosis*. *Br J Nurs* (in press)

9. References in the reference list are arranged alphabetically by the first author's name. As et al is used for all citations with the same first author and two or more co-authors, these references are arranged in chronological order after any references to the same first author writing alone or with one co-author:

Black B (1990) etc.

Black B, Abel C (1987) etc.

Black B, Green X (1985) etc.

Black B, White Z, Green X, Abel C (1979) etc. } All of these are referred to as

Black B, Abel C, White Z (1989) etc. } Black et al in the text

10. If you had two references each with more than two authors (but different authors) but with the same date, e.g.

Smith A, Brown B, White W (1979)

Smith A, White W, Black B (1979)

These would both appear in text as Smith et al (1979). They would therefore have to be referenced as Smith et al (1979a) and Smith et al (1979b).

11. Mc should be alphabetised as if it were Mac.

12. Abbreviation for edition is edn. Abbreviation for editors is eds, and for editor is ed.

1. Turnover lines in references are indented 3 mm.

2. Some examples of frequently used reference entries:

British National Formulary:

In main text: (Joint Formulary Committee, 2010)

In the reference section: Joint Formulary Committee (2010) *British National Formulary 55*. BMA and RPS Publishing, London

Department of Health (DH):

In the main text: Spell out once, put abbreviation in brackets, continue to use abbreviation (Department of Health (DH), 2012). Then (DH, 2014) etc.

In the reference section: Always spell out:

Department of Health (2006b) *Our Health, Our Care, Our Say: A New Direction for Community Services*. White Paper. The Stationery Office, London

Department of Health (2007a) Putting people first: A shared vision and commitment to the transformation of adult social care. <http://tinyurl.com/2nffly> (accessed 31.07.2013)

Department of Health (2007b) Putting people first: Working to make it happen. Adult social care workforce strategy. Interim statement. www.dh.gov.uk/en/SocialCare/workforce/DH_084575 (accessed 31.07.2013)

World Health Organization (WHO):

In the main text: Spell out once, put abbreviation in brackets, continue to use abbreviation (World Health Organization (WHO), 2011).

In the reference section: Always spell out:

World Health Organization (1986) Ottawa Charter For Health promotion.

http://www.euro.who.int/AboutWHO/Policy/20010827_2 (accessed 17.08.2013)

National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE):

National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (2010). NICE clinical guideline 53. Dementia. Supporting people with dementia and their carers in health and social care. <http://guidance.nice.org.uk/cg42> (accessed 30.08.2013)

Conference presentations

Format conference-presentation citations in the style of the following example:

Jahani I (2011) *Getting it right first time*. Presented at: 15th International Pediatric Diabetes Congress (poster B134). Lisbon, Portugal, 12–15 August

REFERENCES (Web)

Make sure web address is not a homepage but leads directly to relevant document. Accessed date is the date the subeditor checks the ref.

Author (1999) *Title*. www.etc.com/index.html (accessed 5.09.2013)

If the web reference is ridiculously long (and requires turning lines), go to <https://bitly.com>.

Paste in your long web references and it will give you a short one.

Ethical principles

The author(s) of all articles must warrant that the submitted manuscript is their original work, has not been published before and is not being considered for publication by another publisher.

Ethic committee approval

Papers describing original work (usually in the Clinical Practice section) need to include a statement that the study obtained ethics approval (or a statement that it was not required).

Photographs

No more than 10 figures (photos should be provided as jpeg or tiff (300dpi)). Figures must be cited in the text. Authors must also ensure that all necessary permissions for the reproduction of copyrighted works (e.g. photographs, figures) not owned by the author(s) have been obtained, and that the manuscript contains no unlawful statements and does not infringe any rights of others.

Conflict of interest statement

It is the journal's editorial policy to ask authors to declare any conflict of interest, including any possible interest, financial or otherwise, that may embarrass the author or the journal if revealed at a later date. If you believe that applies to you, please provide a statement to run at the end of the article.

Peer review process

All articles will undergo double-blind peer review where the article will be sent anonymously to two people who specialise in the subject area of the article.

Reviewers are asked to return constructive comments within two to three weeks. Feedback is returned to authors and a decision made about how to proceed in the following categories: accept, accept with minor revisions, revise and resubmit, reject. Where an article receives two conflicting reviews, the editor will make the final decision.

Proofs

Once the final revised article has been accepted for publication, the corresponding author will receive a PDF copy of the subedited article with author questions (AQs). The corresponding author is then responsible for reviewing content and proofreading the article to ensure accuracy, and returning answers to AQs and other amendments promptly.

Major revisions to the text are NOT possible at this stage. There may be a delay of some months from the date of acceptance to publication date, depending on scheduling. However, we aim for this delay to be no longer than six months and in most cases it will be considerably shorter.

APPENDIX C

BRADEN LETTER OF PERMISSION

Date: February 24, 2017

To: Jennifer Guzman

From: Barbara Braden, PhD, RN, FAAN, Nancy Bergstrom, PhD, RN, FAAN

RE: Permission to use the Braden Scale*

As holders of the official copyright for the Braden Scale for Predicting Pressure Sore Risk and the interventions, we hereby grant permission for the use of the scale in your DNP scholarly project at CSU-Fullerton.

*It is understood that the tool must be printed as it appears on the Braden Scale website (www.bradenscale.com) in relation to title, wording and scoring of each subscale, and the acknowledgement, "Copyright, Braden and Bergstrom, 1988. Reprinted with permission. All rights reserved."

APPENDIX D

BRADEN SCALE

BRADEN SCALE FOR PREDICTING PRESSURE SORE RISK		Date of Assessment
Patient's Name	Evaluator's Name	
<p>SENSORY PERCEPTION ability to respond meaningfully to pressure-related discomfort</p>	<p>1. Completely Limited Unresponsive (loose not mean, flinch, or grasp) to painful stimuli, due to diminished level of consciousness or accident OR OR has a sensory impairment which limits the ability to feel pain or discomfort over 1/3 of body.</p>	<p>4. No Impairment Responds to verbal commands. Has no sensory deficit which would require repositioning or repositioning or repositioning.</p>
<p>MOISTURE degree to which skin is exposed to moisture</p>	<p>1. Constantly Moist Skin is kept moist almost constantly by perspiration, urine, etc. Dried areas (if selected) every time patient is moved or turned.</p>	<p>4. Rarely Moist Skin is usually dry, then only requires changing at routine intervals.</p>
<p>ACTIVITY degree of physical activity</p>	<p>1. Bedfast Confined to bed.</p>	<p>4. Walks Frequently Walks outside room at least twice a day and inside room at least once every two hours during waking hours</p>
<p>MOBILITY ability to change and control body position</p>	<p>1. Completely immobile Does not make even slight changes in body or extremity position without assistance</p>	<p>4. No Limitation Makes major and frequent changes in position without assistance.</p>
<p>NUTRITION usual food intake pattern</p>	<p>1. Very Poor Never eats a complete meal. Usually eats more than 1/3 of any meal (includes 2 or more servings of protein, fat, or carbohydrate products) per day. Takes fluids poorly. Does not take a liquid dietary supplement OR OR is NPO and/or maintained on clear liquids or IV's for more than 5 days.</p>	<p>4. Excellent Eats most of every meal. Never refuses a meal. Usually eats 3 or more servings of meat and dairy products. Occasionally eats between meals. Does not require supplementation.</p>
<p>FRICTION & SHEAR</p>	<p>1. Problem Requires moderate to maximum assistance in moving. Complete lifting without sliding against sheets is impossible. Frequently slides down in bed or chair, requiring frequent repositioning with maximum assistance. Spends considerable time sliding back to throat constraint location.</p>	<p>3. No Apparent Problem Moves in bed and in chair independently and has sufficient muscle strength to lift up completely during move. Maintains good position in bed or chair.</p>
<p>* Copyright Barbara Braden and Nancy Bergstrom, 1988. All rights reserved.</p>		<p>Total Score</p>

Copyright, Braden and Bergstrom, 1988. Reprinted with permission. All rights reserved.

APPENDIX E

AHRQ LETTER OF PERMISSION

DEPARTMENT OF HEALTH AND HUMAN SERVICES
Agency for Healthcare

Research and Quality
5600 Fishers Lane
Rockville, MD 20857
www.ahrq.gov

April 6, 2017
Jennifer Guzman, MSN, RN
DNP candidate, School of Nursing
California State University, Fullerton
Fullerton, CA

Dear Ms. Guzman:

This signed letter constitutes formal permission from the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ) for you to reprint and use Tool IA ("Clinical Staff Attitudes Toward Pressure Ulcer Prevention") from Preventing Pressure Ulcers in Hospitals: A Toolkit for Improving Quality of Care (AHRQ Publication No. 11-0053-EF) in your doctoral research at California State University—Fullerton. Please note on each copy of the Attitudes Questionnaire that it was "Used with permission of the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality; Rockville, MD."

You also have permission to use information from the Toolkit in your thesis or capstone paper, as long as you give proper reference citation to the source of the information. The suggested reference citation for Tool IA is:

Preventing Pressure Ulcers in Hospitals: A Toolkit for Improving Quality of Care.
(Tool IA. " Clinical Staff Attitudes Toward Pressure Ulcer Prevention," in:
Chapter
7-Tools and Resources). September 2012. Agency for Healthcare
Research and Quality; Rockville, MD.
(<https://www.ahrq.gov/professionals/systems/hospital/pressureulcertoolkit/put0017.html#TooloneA>)

You have AHRQ's permission to reprint this letter as an appendix in your thesis/capstone paper. Best wishes with your degree program and your research!

Sincerely,

David I. Lewin, M.Phil.
Health Communications Specialist/Manager of Copyrights &
Permissions Office of Communications
Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality

APPENDIX F

ATTITUDES SURVEY

Views on Pressure Ulcer Prevention

Age: _____ Male/Female/Decline to State

Number of years as RN: _____

Highest level of education: _____

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1. All patients are at potential risk of developing pressure ulcers					
2. Pressure ulcer prevention is time consuming for me to carry out					
3. In my opinion, patients tend not to get as many pressure ulcers nowadays					
4. I do not need to concern myself with pressure ulcer prevention in my practice					
5. Pressure ulcer treatment is a greater priority than pressure ulcer prevention					
6. Continuous assessment of patients will give an accurate account of their pressure ulcer risk					
7. Most pressure ulcers can be avoided					
8. I am less interested in pressure ulcer prevention than other aspects of care					
9. My clinical judgment is better than any pressure ulcer risk assessment tool available to me					
10. In comparison with other areas of care, pressure ulcer prevention is a low priority for me					
11. Pressure ulcer risk assessment should be regularly carried out on all patients during their stay in hospital					

Used with permission of the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality;
Rockville, MD.

APPENDIX G

PDSA LETTER OF PERMISSION

Jennifer Guzman <jennguzman@csu.fullerton.edu>

inquiry reply - use of PDSA model

Bill Bellows <bill@deming.org>

Fri, Feb 24, 2017 at 12:40 PM

To: Jennifer Guzman <jennguzman@csu.fullerton.edu>

Jennifer - greetings from Los Angeles...

Thank you for your inquiry, which I have inserted below:

Comments: I am interested in using the PDSA model as my supporting framework for my Doctorate of Nursing Practice scholarly project. I am writing to request permission to use the model. I will be working with nurses and their use of the Braden scale for predicting patient risk for pressure ulcer development. Thank you for your time and please feel free to contact me with any questions or concerns.

Given the information you have provided, I would welcome the opportunity to connect with you and learn more about your scholarly efforts. Meanwhile,, you are also most welcome to use the PDSA model. All we ask is you include the following statement in your material, "PDSA model used courtesy of The W.

Edwards Deming Institute®."

With travel much of next week, I have a window to connect with you on Tuesday afternoon, between 3 and 6pm. Let me know if this timing works for your schedule. If not, let me know your availability on March 8th or 9th. Thanks!

I look forward to speaking with you and learning more about your research.

Best...

Bill

Bill Bellows

Deputy Director

The W. Edwards Deming Institute®

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APPENDIX H

HILL ROM LETTER OF PERMISSION

May 15, 2017

Jennifer Guzman

Pete Wick
Clinical Outcomes Manager
Hill-Rom

Jennifer

You have our permission to use data collected at [REDACTED] and reported in our 2016 or 2017 International Pressure Ulcer Prevalence survey.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "Pete Wick".

APPENDIX I

TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Purpose (Author, Date)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measurements	Findings	Conclusions/Limitations
<p>Verify the association between PU development, nursing workload, and illness severity and the relationship with Braden Scale scores</p> <p>(Cremasco, Wenzel, Zanei, & Whitaker, 2013)</p>	<p>Prospective descriptive study</p> <p>IVs- Nursing workload, and illness severity</p> <p>DVs- Braden Score and PU presence</p>	<p>Three university hospital ICUs in Sao Paulo, Brazil</p> <p>160 pts</p> <p>Inclusion/exclusion criteria: without PU on ICU admission and minimum 24-hour stay</p>	<p>Demographics (collected from hospital records)</p> <p>NAS 0-177%</p> <p>SAPSII 0-163</p> <p>Braden Scale 0-23</p> <p>GCS 3-15</p> <p>PU presence</p>	<p>Mean age 55.5</p> <p>53.8% women</p> <p>Mean LOS 14.1 days (only from admission or transfer to ICU until discharge or death)</p> <p>Mean BS 12</p> <p>PU incidence 34.4% (58.2% within the first week)</p> <p>NAS>63% in 46.25% of pts</p> <p>Mean SAPSII 39.9</p> <p>No SS r/t mean age and NAS with or without PU</p> <p>Incidence of PU higher in men (p = 0.028)</p> <p>SS of scores between pts with and without PU in following categories: Mean LOS in ICU (p < 0.001) and hospital (p =</p>	<p>Nursing workload, illness severity, LOS, and sex identified as RF PU development</p> <p>Nursing workload identified as protective factor (p = 0.148) may be related to high workload indicating pt being adequately cared for, thereby reducing RF PU</p> <p>SS between Braden scores in PU pts vs pts without PU, but not clinically significant because all were low- may indicate tool is not accurately precise to evaluate PU risk</p> <p>Low specificity of Braden scores- need to take illness severity, LOS and sex into account</p> <p>Note- other factors need to be taken into account when attempting to predict RF PU development besides BS</p>

				0.025), Braden ($p < 0.001$), and SAPSII ($p < 0.002$)	
<p>Assess the viability of modifying the risk classifications of Braden Scale scores</p> <p>(Chen, Cao, Wang, & Huai, 2015)</p>	<p>Retrospective analysis</p> <p>DV- PU incidence</p> <p>IV- modified BS and traditional BS</p>	<p>2,625 pts in ICU (geographic location not mentioned, but supported by Nantong Municipal Science and Technology Bureau, so likely in China)</p> <p>3,000 bed teaching hospital over one year (2013)</p> <p>Pts RF PU on admission or when entering ICU (ie, spinal cord injury, cardiac surgery, long operation time)</p> <p>Excluded if PU on admit or if pt expired</p>	<p>Demographics (age, gender, weight, disease)</p> <p>Braden score</p> <p>PU info (occurrence [yes/no], severity [NPUAP], number of PUs, location, outcome)</p> <p>NPUAP- stages 1-4, unstageable and suspected DTI</p> <p>Collected by nurse experienced in PU care and verified by another nurse</p>	<p>Mean age 59.8 y</p> <p>Mean Braden 15.3</p> <p>PU incidence 3.1% (n = 81)</p> <p>SS ($p < 0.05$) between modified risk categories; no SS between traditional classifications ($p > 0.05$)</p>	<p>The modified risk categories showed SS- ≤ 11 high risk, 12-16 moderate risk and ≥ 17 mild risk</p> <p>Recommend not having a 'no risk' category, as PU incidence was 1.4%</p> <p>Three categories of risk would make interventions clearer and easier to follow</p> <p>Limitations- only one facility, relied on accuracy and completeness of pt records, no analysis by stage of PU r/t small sample size (81)</p> <p>Note- Change in categories of risk to remove 'no risk' to make interventions easier to follow</p>

<p>Evaluate predictive validity of the BS for assessing RF PU (Hyun et al., 2013)</p>	<p>Longitudinal EHR data review DV- PU development IV- Braden Score</p>	<p>3 adult ICUs, 2medical 1 surgical 7,790 pts total 4-year study period Ohio Inclusion criteria: adult, ICU, 1/1/07 to 12/31/10, Exclusion criteria: LOS less than 3 days, PU on admit</p>	<p>Braden Scale 0-23 Demographic info- sex, race, age, LOS</p>	<p>57% male, 82% white, mean age 57.7, mean LOS 10 days PU incidence ranged from 8.1% to 10.5% (n= 154-207 per year) Mean Braden for pts with PU 12.1, mean score for pts without PU 14.2</p>	<p>Braden showed poor predictive validity and accuracy High number of false positives using cutoff of 18 May not reflect ICU pt characteristics well Note- other scales may reflect ICU pt characteristics better- resources may be wasted on pts that show high risk on BS but are not at high risk</p>
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<p>Identify factors that predict r/f PU development in high risk pts</p> <p>(Demarre et al., 2015)</p>	<p>Secondary data analysis of previous RCT</p> <p>DV- PU development</p> <p>IV- one-stage or multistage alternating low-pressure air mattress</p>	<p>5 Belgian hospitals</p> <p>Convenience sample</p> <p>8 geriatric wards and 17 medical wards</p> <p>Inclusion- BS less than 17, presence of non-blanchable erythema were eligible</p> <p>Exclusion- presence of PU, LOS less than 3 days, DNR order, age <18, weight <30kg and >160kg</p>	<p>Demographics</p> <p>Medical history, diagnosis</p> <p>Age, gender, weight, length, incontinence, presence of urinary catheter, body temperature and blood pressure, BS, medical characteristics (diabetes, paralysis, medication), primary diagnosis, ward type, and skin status (non-blanchable erythema and incontinence-associated dermatitis).</p>	<p>Non-blanchable erythema (OR = 5.36; 95% CI 2.4–12.0), having a urogenital disorder (OR = 3.76; 95% CI 1.0–13.7) and higher body temperature (OR = 1.65; 95% CI 1.0–2.7) were independent predictive factors for the development of pressure ulcers</p> <p>44.4% of pts that developed superficial sacral Pus had incontinence associated dermatitis</p> <p>Mean BS 14, median age 80, 60.5% female, 27.5% bedbound and 61.3% chairbound</p> <p>PU incidence 5.7%</p>	<p>Pts with non-blanchable erythema, a urogenital disorder and higher body temperature were at increased risk for developing PU even with the use of preventive measures</p> <p>Limitations- Short follow up period of 14 days, small number of pts that developed severe PU</p> <p>Note- Different findings of predictive factors including temp and diagnosis; highlights importance of regular skin checks</p>
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<p>Evaluate the predictive validity of the Braden scale using the scores measured by nurses throughout hospitalization</p> <p>(Jin, Piao, & Lee, 2015)</p>	<p>Retrospective design- data analysis of electronic medical records</p> <p>DV- PU occurrence</p> <p>IV- age, LOS, BS</p>	<p>University hospital in Seoul between 10/1/08 and 6/30/11</p> <p>Pts with HAPUs (n = 1,305) and pts who did not develop PUs (n = 5,220)</p> <p>Exclusion- PU on admission, stage 1 PU development during hospitalization (RT concern about inexperienced nurses' ability to diagnose)</p>	<p>PU stage I-IV and DTI based on the National Pressure Ulcer Advisory Panel</p> <p>Braden Scale 0-23</p>	<p>Pressure ulcer pts were older (mean of 63 vs 47) and had longer LOS (16 days vs 5 days).</p> <p>PU pts had highest BS at admission. Non PU pts had scores within the normal range at admission, lowest score and closest to discharge.</p>	<p>Cut off BS of 18 for ICU pts and 19 for general pts. Difficulty developing an optimal cut off r/t decreasing number of false positives while also avoiding false negatives.</p> <p>Limitations- pts with stage I PU were excluded. Electronic record was reviewed, always concerns with reliability.</p> <p>Note- This study has a more conservative recommendation for risk categories. Also states that it may be possible to evaluate a pt's risk without the need for a nurse assessment of risk based on clinical characteristics.</p>
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<p>Determine the national and state incidence levels of HAPUs and to describe the clinical outcomes and demographic characteristics and outcomes of these individuals</p> <p>(Lyder et al., 2012)</p>	<p>Retrospective secondary analysis of the national Medicare Patient Safety Monitoring System database</p> <p>DV- PU development</p> <p>IV- comorbidities (COPD, CVD, DM, CHF, corticosteroid use, obesity, and smoking)</p>	<p>Medicare eligible hospitals in United States and territories</p> <p>51,842 randomly selected pts discharged between 1/1/06 and 12/31/07</p> <p>Pts with PU on admission were not excluded, but their charts were reviewed for development of additional PUs</p>	<p>Demographics, medical diagnoses, outcomes (mortality, LOS, and Readmission)</p>	<p>4.5% developed HAPU (n = 2,313)</p> <p>Mortality risk odds ratios were 2.81 for in-pt and 1.69 within 30 days of discharge; odds ratio of 1.33 for readmission within 30 days.</p> <p>Risk adjusted LOS for pts with no PU was 4.8 days and 11.2 days for pts with HAPUs.</p> <p>5.8% PU prevalence rate on admission.</p>	<p>Individuals who developed PUs were more likely to die during the hospital stay, have generally longer hospital lengths of stay, and be readmitted within 30 days after discharge.</p> <p>Specific chronic diseases may increase vulnerability to PU.</p> <p>Limitations- Pts with PU at admission would not have new PUs on the same body region counted. Study unable to capture reliable staging.</p> <p>Note- One day prevalence may not reflect properly- patients with HAPUs have longer LOS so will be more likely to be counted. May also miss PU that have not developed yet.</p>
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Note. BS = Braden Score; DNR = do not resuscitate; DTI = deep tissue injury; DV = dependent variable; GCS = Glasgow Coma Scale; ICU = intensive care unit; IV = Independent Variable; LOS = length of stay; NAS = Nursing Activities Score; NPUAP = National Pressure Ulcer Advisory Panel; Pt = patient; PU = Pressure Ulcer; r/t = related to; RF = risk for; SAPSII = Simplified Acute Physiology Score; SS = statistical significance

APPENDIX J

TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Purpose (Author, Date)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measurements	Findings	Conclusions/Limitations
The purpose of this quality improvement project was to increase nursing compliance with skin assessments and ultimately decrease HAPUs in an acute rehabilitation center. (Revello & Fields, 2012)	Performance improvement projects IV-educational sessions (group or 1:1), skin rounds, nursing assistant participation, and sharing of pressure ulcer data DV-compliance with skin checks	Sharp Grossmont Hospital, a 536 bed, Magnet designated, tertiary care hospital in San Diego County, with a 30-bed mixed acute rehabilitation and medical/surgical nursing care unit Approximately 40 licensed nurses and 20 nursing assistants Inclusion criteria: all licensed nurses and nursing assistants were included	Education attendance Compliance with documented skin assessment within 24 hours of admission HAPU incidence Wound log including: Wound stages I-IV, wound area, presence of picture	100% of staff received the education either in group or 1:1 format 100% compliance with admission assessment in 24hours Zero incidence of HAPU Logs were not completed when educator or lead nurse were absent	Sharing the data encouraged nurses to continue the work. The education and interdisciplinary approach were important. Note: individual nurses were counselled when skin breakdown was discovered that had not been charted. Errors in staging or documentation were presented in staff meetings. PT, OT, CNAs included in skin checks. CNAs given small thank-you gifts. Nurses had not been doing skin checks at the beginning of the shift Difficulty maintaining skin care champion, logs not always completed

Purpose (Author, Date)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measurements	Findings	Conclusions/Limitations
<p>The purpose of this study was to determine if an isolation educational program which included visual demonstrations of cross-contamination during breaks in isolation procedures increased nursing staff knowledge of and adherence to isolation procedures.</p> <p>(Anderson, Johnson, & Wendt, 2015)</p>	<p>A pretest-posttest, single group, quasi-experimental design</p> <p>IV- education program with visual demonstration of cross contamination</p> <p>DV- knowledge of and adherence to isolation procedures</p>	<p>RNs, LPNs, and CNAs with consent n=30 (10 chose not to participate)</p> <p>36-bed medical oncology unit in southeastern United States</p> <p>Inclusion/exclusion : working at least 8 hours/week and permanently assigned to the medical oncology unit. Staff on orientation were excluded.</p>	<p>Pre-and Posttest knowledge questions (seven multiple-choice questions)</p> <p>Black light examination post procedure and decontamination</p> <p>Demographic information</p> <p>Critical behavior checklist (four behaviors entering and four behaviors exiting) during observation (staff were not aware they were being observed)</p>	<p>Isolation knowledge significantly increased after the education program, from a pretest score of 71% to a posttest score of 86% (t26 = 5.11, p<0.0001)</p> <p>Observation of behavioral adherence to isolation policies and procedures for entering/exiting the isolation room were similar before (85%) and after (82%) the isolation educational program (chi square=1.54, p=0.67)</p>	<p>Inter rater reliability was established in a trial phase</p> <p>Newer nurses may be more likely to adhere to strict guidelines while more experienced nurses may judge an intervention in an acute situation to take precedence over isolation procedures</p> <p>Limitations- only one unit, researchers known to staff, only 12 of 30 staff available for posttest observation</p> <p>Note: Comments after black light demonstration- “This convinces me!” “Wow, who knew?” “I thought I was doing a good job with hand washing.” “I did not know my pants leg was touching the bed below the gown.”</p>

Purpose (Author, Date)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measurements	Findings	Conclusions/Limitations
To estimate the frequency of use of PRSS and whether or not the use was related to higher PU risk (Baumgarten et al., 2010)	Prospective cohort study between 2004 and 2007	Patients (n= 658) 65+ hip fracture surgery with consent	Demographics PRSS use Presence of PU	Mean age 83.2 (6.6) 23.1% male 98% white Mean LOS 5.9 days (3.2)	PRSS use should be based on PU risk, but seemed to be more r/t facility factors Providers may feel that patients in rehab are not high risk for PU
	Assessed at baseline and on alternating days for 21 days IV- PU risk DV- use of PRSS	Nine hospitals of the Baltimore Hip Studies network and 105 post-acute facilities	Braden score 6-23 Subjective Global Assessment of Nutritional Status Rand Sickness at Admission Scale Charlson comorbidity scale Activity, continence and orientation	PRSS use 36.4% More likely use with higher Braden score OR 1.2; and higher with presence of PU OR 1.2- highest use in acute care (rehab setting less than half and skilled nursing less than one quarter). Readmission to acute care use of PRSS OR 0.6.	Note: providers are not compliant with guidelines for use of PRSS in patients with high risk for PU

Purpose (Author, Date)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measurements	Findings	Conclusions/Limitations
To evaluate whether an educational intervention with a year of implementation has changed nursing behavior when faced with a deteriorating patient (Ludikhuizen et al., 2011)	Quasi-experimental	1000-bed teaching hospital	Demographics	Median age 28	One of the non-trained wards had significantly older and more experienced nurses. When their results were removed, the differences between trained and non-trained responses were statistically significant Note: despite having education and extensive follow up throughout the year, adherence to the protocol was very low. Study concludes that they need to find more effective implementation strategies.
	Trained nurses received education and extensive follow-up	Six nursing units- three trained in use of MEWS and SBAR and three not trained	Use of MEWS Use of SBAR	Trained nurses: only 1 (4%) used SBAR when contacting physician, MEWS was only calculated four times and only one nurse followed protocol and called physician (but did not mention the MEWS score)	
	IV- education and follow up	All RNs (n=95); 47 trained and 48 not trained	Following the hospital protocol about contacting physician	Even when vitals were measured, only 60% of the time were they conveyed to physician	
	DV- adherence to protocol				

Purpose (Author, Date)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measurements	Findings	Conclusions/Limitations
Evaluate adherence to best practice, describe care practices, and explore relationship between care practices and demographics (Cason et al., 2007)	Cross sectional survey	Critical care nurses (n= 1200) taking care of adult patients in US acute care settings Attendees of either the American Association of Critical Care Nurses National Teaching Institute or training from the Barbara Clark Mims Associates	Demographics Oral Care of Ventilated Patients Questionnaire including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Handwashing • Glove use • Suctioning practices • Elevation of bed • Ventilator Associated Pneumonia rates and causative organisms • Use of Yankauer 	Mean age 43 (9) mean years of experience 14 82% compliance with hand-washing guidelines, 75% wear gloves, 50% elevated the head of the bed, 33% performed subglottic suctioning, 50% reported formal protocol for oral care Hospitals with protocol had greater compliance with hand washing, head-of-bed elevation, oral care, familiarity with rates of ventilator-associated pneumonia and the organisms involved	Gap between knowledge and adherence Rates may have been higher than in general population because these were nurses involved in educational advancement- more likely to be knowledgeable Note: compliance is not as high as should be expected, but nurses were more knowledgeable and more compliant in facilities with protocol outlining behavior

Note. CNA= certified nursing assistant; DV= dependent variable; HAPU= hospital acquired pressure ulcers; IV= independent variable; LPN= licensed practical nurse; MEWS= modified early warning score; OR= odds ratio; OT= occupational therapy; PRSS= pressure redistributing support surfaces; PT= physical therapy; PU= pressure ulcer; RN= registered nurse; r/t= related to; SBAR= situation-background-assessment-recommendation communication tool